

by C.P. blue value method. With the aeration the peroxide value has also increased from 6 to 50 whereas there is no appreciable increase in its acid value. It may be mentioned here that the iodine value of sesame oil is nearer to that of arachis oil whose iodine value generally varies from 85 to 99. But the rate of formation of peroxide in the former case is considerably enhanced and consequently the destruction of vitamin-A in this oil is much rapid when compared to similar destruction of vitamin-A concentrate dissolved in arachis oil as noted by Basu (*loc. cit.*) and Basu and Sen-Gupta (*loc. cit.*). For such rapid destruction of vitamin no other experiment was conducted after incorporation of any suitable antioxidant. It may be noted that the use of antioxidants would retard the peroxide formation as also the rate of destruction of vitamin-A, but since it is obvious from the observations made in this laboratory that in sesame oil peroxide formation is much faster than in arachis oil which is also easily available, it was not considered to be of any practical value to try the effect of antioxidants for this work.

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BENGAL IMMUNITY RESEARCH LABORATORY,
CALCUTTA.

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STUDIES IN FRIES MIGRATION. PART II. THE FRIES MIGRATION OF ESTERS OF 7-HYDROXY-3-ALKYL-4-METHYL-6-ETHYLCUMARINS

By V. M. THAKOR AND N. M. SHAH

The Fries rearrangement of the esters of 7-hydroxy-3-alkyl-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarins has been studied. It is observed that the alkyl groups exert but little influence on the course of the migration. The migration products have been subjected to Kostanecki acetylation and various coumarino- α - or γ -pyrones are formed.

In continuation of our work described in the previous part of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 199) we have investigated the Fries rearrangement of different esters of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl- as well as of 7-hydroxy-3-alkyl-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarins. The results obtained confirm our previous conclusions that (1) below a certain temperature the migration does not take place: and, if the migration is carried out at higher temperature, the product gets charred (*cf.* Tarbell and Fanta, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2169); (2) different acyl groups require different temperatures for migration, which vary according to the nature and size of the acyl group, *e.g.*, benzoyl group requires a higher temperature for migration than the acetyl (Rosenmund and Schmurr, *Annalen*, 1928, 460, 56; Baltzly and Bass, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 4292) and (3) the use of aluminium chloride in proportions higher than three moles leads to the contamination of the resulting products with impurities.

In all cases, the migration was smooth and the different substituents present in the coumarin nucleus had little inhibitory influence on the course of the rearrangement. In all cases, the product obtained was found to be 7-hydroxy-3-alkyl-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetyl- or 8-benzoyl-coumarin, since (i) it gave strong colouration with alcoholic ferric

chloride, and dissolved in alkali with non-fluorescent yellow colour and (ii) on Kostanecki acetylation with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, coumarino- α - or - γ -pyrone was obtained (IV).

EXPERIMENTAL

General Method of carrying out the Migration.—The acetyl or benzoyl derivative of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin (II, $\text{R} = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{Me}$ or Ph) or of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-3-alkylcoumarin (II, $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, \text{C}_3\text{H}_7, \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{Me}$ or Ph) (1 mol.) was intimately mixed with aluminium chloride (3.3 mols.) and the mixture protected by CaCl_2 guard-tube was heated in an oil-bath at a particular temperature for a definite period. When the evolution of the hydrochloric acid gas slackened, the mixture was cooled, and ice and hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) added and the solid that separated was collected and identified. The migration of 7-acetoxy- and 7-benzoyloxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin was investigated under different conditions and the results are tabulated below.

TABLE I

(a) *Fries migration of 7-acetoxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin.*

Formation of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetyl-coumarin (III, $\text{R} = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{Me}$).

Temp.	Unreacted ester	De-acetylated product	Migrated product	Remarks
115-120°	0.4 g.	0.9 g.	0.1 g.	Impure, m.p. 129-135°
130-140°	..	..	2.0	Pure, m.p. 140°
150-160°	..	..	1.0	Charred mass which on repeated crystallisations gave green crystals, m.p. 133-35°

All migrations were carried out with 2.45 g. of the coumarin ester,

(b) *Fries migration of 7-benzoyloxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin.*Formation of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-benzoylcoumarin (III, R=H; R₁=Ph).

Temp.	Unreacted ester.	De-benzoylated product.	Migrated product.	Remarks.
120-130°	0.8 g.	0.6 g.	Indication	Gave FeCl ₃ colour test but pure product could not be isolated.
135-140°	0.2	1.0	0.2 g.	m.p. 158-60°
150-160°	..	..	1.5	m.p. 160°
175-180°	..	..	0.7	Charred product which on repeated crystallisations gave crystals, m.p. 158-160°

All migrations were carried out with 2 g. of the coumarin ester.

The acetoxy or benzoyloxy derivatives of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-3-alkyl-coumarins were similarly studied and the results are tabulated below :

(1) The acetoxy derivatives were heated at 130-140° for one hour. (2) The benzoyloxy derivatives were heated at 155-160° for the same period. Otherwise the procedure was similar. (3) Unless otherwise stated, the solvent used for crystallisation is alcohol. (4) All the migration products dissolve in alkali giving a non-fluorescent yellow solution and give colour with ferric chloride in alcoholic solutions; the acetyl compounds give cherry red, while the benzoyl compounds give violet colour.

TABLE II

No.	Original compound.	Migration product : Properties etc.	Acetyl derivative of the migration product.	Kostanecki acetylation of the migration product.
1	7-Acetoxy 3 : 4-dimethyl-6-ethylcoumarin	7-Hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylcoumarin, m.p. 125° (Desai & Mavani, <i>Proc. Ind. Acad. Sc.</i> , 1941, 14A, 100 give m.p. 121°)		3 : 4 : 2' -Trimethyl-6-ethyl-3' -acetylcoumarino-(7 : 8 : 5' : 6')-γ-pyrone, needles, m.p. 214.5° from benzene. (Found : C, 70.3; H, 5.8. C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₅ requires C, 69.9; H, 5.5 per cent).
2	7-Acetoxy-3 : 6-diethyl-4-methylcoumarin	7-Hydroxy-3 : 6-diethyl-4-methyl-8-acetylcoumarin, m.p. 149.5°. (Found : C, 69.8; H, 6.8. C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₅ requires C, 70.0; H, 6.6 per cent).	Colourless needles, m.p. 109° (Found : C, 67.4; H, 6.4. C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₅ requires C, 67.7; H, 6.3 per cent).	
3	7-Acetoxy-3-propyl-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin	7-Hydroxy-3-propyl-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylcoumarin, m.p. 128°. Desai and Mavani give m.p. 129° (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	Colourless cubes, m.p. 128.9° (Found : C, 68.8; H, 6.9. C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₅ requires C, 69.1; H, 6.7 per cent).	3-Propyl-4 : 2' -dimethyl-6-ethyl-3' -acetylcoumarino-(7 : 8 : 5' : 6')-γ-pyrone, needles, m.p. 191.2° (Found : C, 71.0; H, 6.4. C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₅ requires C, 71.2; H, 6.2 per cent).
4	7-Acetoxy-3-butyl-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin	7-Hydroxy-3-butyl-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylcoumarin, Desai & Mavani (<i>loc. cit.</i>) give m.p. 124°	Colourless crystals, m.p. 120°. (Found : C, 69.5; H, 7.1. C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₅ requires C, 69.8; H, 6.98 per cent).	3-Butyl-4 : 2' -dimethyl-6-ethyl-3' -acetylcoumarino-(7 : 8 : 5' : 6')-γ-pyrone, needles from acetic acid, m.p. 182° (Found : C, 71.5; H, 6.6. C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₅ requires C, 71.7; H, 6.5 per cent).

TABLE II—(contd.)

No.	Original compound.	Migration product : Properties etc.	Acetyl derivative of the migration product.	Kostanecki acetylation of the migration product.
5	7-Acetoxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin	7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylcoumarin, m.p. 140° (Desai & Ekhlās, <i>Proc. Ind. Acad. Sc.</i> , 1938, 8A, 194 give m.p. 139°; Limaye & Limaye give m.p. 135° <i>Rasayanam</i> 1941; 201)	Colourless needles, m.p. 131°. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 5.8. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 66.7; H, 5.6 per cent).	4:2'-Dimethyl-6-ethyl-3'-acetylcoumarino-(7:8:5':6')- γ -pyrone, needles, m.p. 192°
6	7-Benzoyloxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin	7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-benzoylcoumarin, m.p. 160°	Colourless needles, m.p. 154-55°. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 5.3. $C_{21}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 72.0; H, 5.1 per cent).	4-Methyl-6-ethyl-4'-phenylcoumarino-(7:8:5':6')- α -pyrone, needles, m.p. 144° (Found: C, 75.4; H, 5.1. $C_{21}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 75.9; H, 4.8 per cent).
7	7-Benzoyloxy-3:4-dimethyl-6-ethylcoumarin	7-Hydroxy-3:4-dimethyl-6-ethyl-8-benzoylcoumarin, m.p. 138-39°. (Found: C, 74.4; H, 5.7. $C_{20}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 74.5; H, 5.6 per cent).	Colourless needles, m.p. 168.9°. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 5.6. $C_{22}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 72.5; H, 5.6 per cent).	3:4-Dimethyl-6-ethyl-4'-phenylcoumarino-(7:8:5':6')- α -pyrone, needles, m.p. 164.5° (Found: C, 76.1; H, 5.5. $C_{22}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 76.3; H, 5.2 per cent).
8	7-Benzoyloxy-3:6-diethyl-4-methylcoumarin	7-Hydroxy-3:6-diethyl-4-methyl-8-benzoylcoumarin, m.p. 139°. (Found: C, 74.8; H, 6.1. $C_{21}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.95 per cent).	Colourless needles, m.p. 131.2° (Found: C, 72.8; H, 6.0. $C_{23}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 73.0; H, 5.8 per cent).	
9	7-Benzoyloxy-3-propyl-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin	7-Hydroxy-3-propyl-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-benzoylcoumarin, m.p. 134°. (Found: C, 75.3; H, 6.4. $C_{22}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 75.4; H, 6.3 per cent).	Colourless needles, m.p. 141.2°. (Found: C, 73.2; H, 6.3. $C_{24}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, 73.5; H, 6.1 per cent).	3-Propyl-4-methyl-6-ethyl-4'-phenylcoumarino-(7:8:5':6')- α -pyrone, needles, m.p. 194.5° (Found: C, 76.9; H, 6.0. $C_{24}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 77.0; H, 5.9 per cent).
10	7-Benzoyloxy-3-butyl-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin	7-Hydroxy-3-butyl-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-benzoylcoumarin, m.p. 129° (Found: C, 75.6; H, 6.7. $C_{23}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 75.8; H, 6.6 per cent).	Needles, m.p. 134-35°. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 6.5. $C_{25}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 73.9; H, 6.4 per cent).	

The migration products 1 to 5 described here crystallise from acetic acid as yellow flaky needles; while the rest crystallise from alcohol as needles.

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